

ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

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PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PREPARING GIRLS OF MARRIAGE AGE FOR NEW SOCIAL ROLES

ANNOTATION

This article talks about the views of Eastern thinkers regarding the preparation of girls for family life, the research conducted in this regard, problems, and the unique psychology of girls of marriageable age.

Key words: Uzbek families, female students, family, society, ethnic characteristics, family values, position, independent life, maternal role, image of an ideal mother.

TURMUSH QURISH YOSHIDAGI QIZLARNI YANGI IJTIMOIIY ROLLARGA TAYYORLASHNING PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada qizlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash borasida Sharq mutafakkirlarining qarashlari, bu borada olib borilgan tadqiqotlar, muammolar, turmush qurish yoshidagi qizlarning o'ziga xos psixologiyasi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zbek oilalari, talaba qizlar, oila, jamiyat, etnik xususiyatlar, oilaviy qadriyatlar, pozitsiya, mustaqil hayot, onalik roli, ideal ona obrazi.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПОДГОТОВКИ ДЕВУШЕК БРАЧНОГО ВОЗРАСТА К НОВЫМ СОЦИАЛЬНЫМ РОЛЯМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассказывается о взглядах восточных мыслителей на подготовку девушек к семейной жизни, исследованиях, проводимых в этом направлении, проблемах и уникальной психологии девушек на выданье.

Ключевые слова: узбекские семьи, студентки, семья, общество, этнические особенности, семейные ценности, позиция, самостоятельная жизнь, материнская роль, образ идеальной матери.

The increasing number of family separations in the world, the prevailing unhealthy environment in families and the failure of marriages cause many internal mental tensions, conflicts, and negative consequences, and the reason for this is that in many cases young people are not ready for family life, family life the formation of wrong ideas about it, the need to study the problem of ensuring family strength and the relevance of research in this regard.

In world educational and research institutions, special attention is paid to scientific research on the issues of identifying socio-psychological factors that have a negative impact on strong family relationships, establishing mutual relations in places of socialization at different levels that affect the individual, and stabilizing the psychological environment. being directed. In this regard, it is necessary to find solutions to the work of strengthening the family institution through a special scientific, practical, new approach, to change the attitude of young people towards their role in the family and society, and to get rid of problematic situations of various levels that arise in interpersonal relations Scientific research of the methods of psychological influence of education, development of scientific conclusions based on socio-psychological analysis of pedagogical-psychological aspects of various negative manifestations occurring in the upbringing of boys and girls of marriageable age remain among the urgent problems of the time.

In recent years, the necessary legal and regulatory frameworks have been created in our republic to educate and prepare the young generation for an independent life. "...Unfortunately, among married young people, there are situations where people imagine life lightly and do not understand that the family is sacred. It is necessary to further strengthen the foundations of the family, which is sacred for us, to fill the work of creating an atmosphere of harmony and mutual respect in households with concrete content... can be a solid foundation for learning.

PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", PF-5938 dated February 18, 2020 "Social and No. PF-81 of March 1, 2022 "On measures to improve the spiritual environment, further support the neighborhood institution, and bring the system of work with family and women to a new level" and working with women, the implementation of large-scale strategic measures defined within the framework of the Decree and other regulatory documents on measures to improve the support system of the neighborhood and religious serves at the level.

Review of literature: Some aspects of issues related to the preparation of girls for family life, especially motherhood, and the creation and improvement of the system of parent-child relations in our republic were discussed by psychologists F.A. Akramova, R. Abdullaeva, H. Abdusamatov, R. Dushanov, V. M. Karimova, Kh.K. Karimov, N.Kh. Lutfullaeva, G. Niyazmetova, Z.A. Rasulova, F. Rozikulov, U.S. Saribaeva, N.A. Soginov, R.S. Samarov, B.M. Umarov, M. Utepbergenov, M. Fayziyeva, G'.B. Shoumarov, G.Kh. Yunusova., U.D. Kadirov and others conducted scientific research.

In January-June, the number of divorces in Uzbekistan amounted to 25,400, which is 828 more than in the corresponding period of 2022. This was reported by the Statistics Agency.

In the first 6 months of this year, Fergana region recorded the highest number of divorces. 3,107 families were divorced in the region in half a year. Tashkent city (2,989) and Andijan region (2,854) are in the next places.

For half a year, the number of divorces with 1 child was 13,186, divorces with 2 or more children were 5,505. The average age of divorced persons was 37.7 years for men and 33.2 years for women. These statistics show that preparing girls for family life is one of the urgent issues of today.

In the researches of Russian scientists Yu.I. Semenov, Masherov, Yu.T. Timofeev, it was shown that the origin of conflict situations in the family is also related to changes in the spheres covering the entire human lifestyle. Z. B. Sikevych and Yu. A. Possella studied the specific characteristics of family relations in brides and grooms of the same or different nationalities. Yu.S. Kotelnikova was one of the first to systematically study the psychological characteristics of abnormal crises in young families [2].

G. V. Lagonda tried to thoroughly study the theory of expectations from marital relations (expecting the results of dreams). In his research, S.A. Garmaev made special studies about the culture of family relations of people belonging to the Christian religion. The scientific researches of Ye.M. Savina highlighted the important relationship system in the family during the period when the child is expected to be born (during the mother's pregnancy). The culture of mutual relations between husband and wife is also confirmed by the results of the study of real family life conducted by American researchers V. Metyuza and K. Mikhanovich. In the course of research, more than a dozen necessary differences between happy and unhappy families (conditionally) have been shown. Divorce researcher Diane Wagen, who has studied the relationship between couples who are separating during a divorce, found that in most cases, before the physical separation, the spouses remain different people socially and spiritually.

Judet Wallerstein and John Kelly studied the lives of children of sixty divorced families in California, and noted that the negative consequences of divorce are extremely difficult for children. Ye.Burgess, P.Vollin, L.Terman and M.Odema, G.Roland based on their extensive research noted that several types of qualities and qualities specific to partners should match in marital satisfaction. L. Vygotsky, D. Elkonin, A. N. Leontev, G. Andreeva-Theories of Russian psychologists' functional approach to personality. The concept of social imagination in social psychology (S. Moscovichi, J. Codol, A. Donsov, T. Emelyanova, V. Karimova, etc.), theories on determining the process of reflection of family life activity (A. Kharchev, S. Golod, Z. Yankova, H. Yurkevich, V. Sisenko, N. Solovev, D. Kutsar, T. Mishina).

Khidirova Firuza Farkhodovna in her candidate's dissertation entitled "Pedagogical conditions for preparing girls for independent family life in the family" pedagogically explained the problems of preparing girls for independent family life in the family.

O. E. Eshmurodov's scientific research on the topic "Social and psychological factors of ensuring family stability" talks about family relations, the role of men and women in the family, the formation of family values in them, the formation of family imaginations in growing boys and girls [4].

D.T. Ismatova's candidate's dissertation on the topic "Social-psychological features of correction of emotional stress in family relationships" describes the attitude of family members to emotional-emotional stress in adolescents, important psychological changes during this period the word goes.

Content: Currently, in the establishment of the new statehood of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the laws of global and national statehood development have been harmoniously combined. Since the change of society's life depends on the family and its members, the study and analysis of this problem is an urgent process. Each nation pays special attention to the family and the process related to it, and transmits knowledge, ideas and values about the family from generation to generation. Family as a social institution is classified and studied taking into account the age, profession, number of children, age of marriage, nationality of the spouses, territorial residence of its members. Just as the health of the family environment depends primarily on the woman, the health of the spiritual environment in the society directly depends on the family and the mother who is responsible for family upbringing.

Our future mothers are today's young girls. According to one of our lexicographers, Abu Abdullah Rudaki, "If you want to destroy any nation, take out their daughters - future mothers." "If you want to elevate any nation, teach their daughters - their future mothers to good upbringing and good morals" - is one of the current topics.

If the girls of the nation are educated, well-educated and intelligent, and are fully prepared for family life, the environment in the family will be healthy and the family will be strong and prosperous. That is why girls' moral and psychological preparation for family life, their psychological maturity is important.

It is known that in our holy religion Islam, the "Holy Qur'an" and Hadiths, which are considered its main sources, contain valuable information and sharia laws about all aspects of family life and marital relations. Polygamy is strictly forbidden in Zoroastrianism. At the same time, celibacy is also condemned. If a girl who has reached adulthood does not disobey the opinion of her parents and the community and deliberately does not get married, she is punished by being put in a sack and beaten [3].

A special place is given to the issue of women in the set of moral norms of Zoroastrianism. Because the family is considered sacred in Zoroastrianism, it is not allowed to annul the marriage for other reasons, including provocation, slander, disagreement between the husband and wife, and the excuse of not being able to get along with the parents.

In general, both in Zoroastrianism and in Islam, it is mentioned that both parties are equal and worthy in marriage. According to marriage rules and life experiences, it is preferable for the bride and groom to be close to each other in lineage, social status, knowledge, taste, knowledge, and property. Therefore, in the eastern nations, serious attention is paid to preparing young people for family marriage, finding their match and marrying them. The structure of family values is also influenced by the nationality of our young people who are getting married, because religion, national and cultural traditions of the family leave a certain mark on the belief system of a person. The process of getting used to the values of another nation is somewhat difficult for our young people, who grew up surrounded by the values instilled in their family environment since childhood. This can cause our young people to break up their families.

Summarizing all the above points, the process of preparing our young people for family life and forming the right ideas in them is a very complicated process, and in this process, we should pay special attention to every detail. In order for the family to be strong and family members to feel happy, it is important that a woman feels her place and happiness in the family. Only a happy person can share happiness with others.

From the research conducted to study family problems, it became known that family problems are discord in mutual relations, lack of self-control, dissatisfaction with spouse, boring life, division of family duties, because it originates from the behavior and character traits of family members, such as quarrelsomeness, arrogance, imperfection in behavior, material difficulties, squeamishness. We are sure that man is looking for an ideal person. We have learned that in many cases, spouses are not satisfied with each other (dissatisfaction with work duties), suspicion, criticism, and reprimands cause many problems. Family members believed that it was a lack of mutual understanding in the family, that their character traits did not correspond to each other, and some of them believed that it was the woman's displeasure and reprimands that put herself above the man. It became clear that the root cause of family problems is the lack of pedagogical and psychological knowledge in families. For this, it is necessary to carry out extensive work in this regard in the neighborhoods, to carry out neighborhood gatherings in cooperation with families, to prepare girls for family life, first of all, it is necessary to solve the issues of increasing the psychological literacy of their mothers, increasing their trust in psychologists and pedagogues [2].

In preparing our daughters for family life, it is necessary to give them knowledge about the beautiful sides of family life as well as the ups and downs of life. For example, if you familiarize yourself with the problems mentioned below, which are encountered in many families, they will not be confused when they face difficulties when they step into the big life, and they will be able to get out of this situation by choosing a rational way.

Results: In our Uzbek nation, the family has been considered a sacred place since ancient times. Of course, if the family is healthy and strong, peace and harmony will be achieved in the neighborhood. Peace and stability prevail in the state only when the neighborhood and the country are strong. It can be seen that issues of family life are becoming one of the priority areas of current research.

Today, in our Republic, important work is being done to ensure family stability and to prepare girls for the family. These tasks and problems reduce the number of divorces, create a healthy psychological environment in families, increase the moral and material well-being of society, and serve as an important factor in raising children. The reason is the increase in the number of strong families and a lifestyle based on active creativity in young people brought up in this family, social activity in all areas of society, high quality of citizenship, mental, spiritual and physical health, high civility in work, interaction, communication, will embody such qualities as being kind to others. In fact, the psychologically healthy environment created in the family serves to strengthen people's social positions in the society [6].

At this point, it is permissible to list the family values that should be instilled in our daughters:

- meaning that is important for every member of the family - every family should know need and love;
- mutual respect - accepting the thoughts, feelings and passions of another person;
- honesty - if there is no such value in the family, it means not respecting the person of another person;
- forgiveness - it is important to learn to forgive people who have made a mistake;
- responsibility - this value is necessary for other family members to be calm, because they know that there are people they can trust;
- communication - this value helps strengthen the family, the weakening of communication leads to misunderstanding and family breakdown;
- traditions are one of the most important values of the family, it is the uniqueness of you and your loved ones.

Therefore, every girl getting married should have psychological literacy, acquire communication skills, be able to positively solve family problems, create a healthy psychological environment for her husband and children under any circumstances, and be exemplary in family relationships. they should make their contribution with the services of happiness in the upbringing of children [4].

Conclusions and suggestions: It are necessary to prepare girls of marriageable age for motherhood, and one of the important aspects of motherhood preparation is that girls are not fully prepared for the responsibility of motherhood, they need to search more for full confidence in their responsibility of motherhood. and that there is a high desire to obtain specific knowledge and that girls raised in a dysfunctional family are more worried about the role of motherhood, lack of knowledge in taking responsibility as a result of the lack of "role models" in their imaginations, girls' ideas about family life and "ideal mother" taking into account the fact that it is manifested in a way based on various stereotypes, which leads to the formation of "deceptive" ideas in young people's views on motherhood and is a psychological barrier, it is determined in the research that it is the formation of reproductive culture in the sisters of teenage Uzbek girls and the sexual sphere to multiply and widely promote age-appropriate medical-psychological methods that provide scientific information and knowledge about being a healthy mother, to establish a healthy lifestyle in preparing girls for motherhood, to educate about family It is important to create ideas, create a reproductive culture, and carry out propaganda about the importance of their education in educational institutions.

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